

ON THE IMPACT FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF INTERLEAVED CROSS-PLY CF/EP-LAMINATES

Q. YUAN and J. KARGER-KOCSIS

Institute for Composite Materials Ltd., University of Kaiserslautern, PO Box 3049,
D-67663 Kaiserslautern, FRG

ABSTRACT

It was established that the test configuration strongly affects the impact fatigue response of carbon fiber (CF) reinforced cross-ply laminates with tough, adhesive (A) interleaving. Instrumented impact fatigue was performed on composite beams and plates in three-point bending (Charpy method) and falling weight impact (IFWI), respectively. The ranking of the damage tolerance of the composite plates from IFWI did not match with that from the Charpy tests. Based on the IFWI results the damage tolerance of the plates increased with increasing number of the interleaves. No such correlation could be stated for the Charpy tests. This can be attributed to differences in the loading mode (uni- and biaxial) and impactor shape in the related test methods. The most beneficial location of the A layer(s) could not be defined unequivocally. The damage zone development was followed by different techniques, such as light microscopy, ultrasonic C-scan, X-ray radiography and discussed.

Keywords: Charpy, composite, damage, failure, falling dart, impact, laminate, NDT, toughening

1. INTRODUCTION

Out-of-plane impact of polymeric composites of different lay-ups generally results in a severe loss both in stiffness and strength characteristics. One of the most promising way to overcome this difficulty and enhance the damage tolerance of composites composed of unidirectional (UD) fiber reinforced layers is the interleaving, i.e. incorporation of soft, tough, generally fiberfree layers into the laminate [1]. Several works reported on the residual mechanical properties of carbon fiber (CF) reinforced epoxy-based (EP) laminates with interleaf after impact loading (e.g.[2] with references therein). Less attention was paid, however, to the effects of repeated impact loading [3] (impact fatigue) at different test configurations and to the lay-up of the composite plates including not only the stacking sequence [4] but also the position of the interleaf, adhesive (A) layers. Aims of the present contribution are: i) to compare the impact fatigue behavior of composite beams and plates (in instrumented impact bending and falling weight impact, IFWI, respectively), ii) to study the damage growth by different techniques, and iii) to establish the right positioning of the A layers in the lay-up of composites of high damage tolerance.

2. EXPERIMENTALS

2.1. Materials

CF-EP laminates were prepared from 16 plies composed of Celion CF G30-500/Rigidite 5212 prepregs, cured according to the guidelines of the manufacturer (BASF AG, Ludwigshafen, FRG). The layer array of the composites was a cross-ply version with one or more interleaf layers (A) as

listed in Table 1. The interleaf of a thickness of 0.1 mm (surface mass: 240 g/m²) was a proprietary compound of BASF, laminated on a polyester fabric. Beam and plate specimens were cut from the composite panels (cf. Figure 1). As reference served a noninterleaved laminate with the same lay-up (No. 2 according to Table 1). A UD-laminate of 16 plies (No. 1) was also included into this study.

No	Lay-up
No 1	Unidirectional (UD)
No 2	$[(0/90)_{2s}]_s$
No 3	$(0/90)_{2s}/A/(0/90)_{2s}$
No 4	$(0/90)_2/A/(90/0)_2/(0/90)_{2s}$
No 5	$(0/90)_2/A/(90/0)_2/A/(0/90)_{2s}$
No 6	$(0/90)_2/A/(90/0)_2/A/(0/90)_2/A/(90/0)_2$

Table 1. Code and lay-up of the composite laminates tested
 Note: the impacted surface is on the left-hand side

2.2. Impact Testing and Failure Characterization

The impact behavior of the laminates was studied at room temperature (RT) at monotonic increased critical (fracture) and subcritical loadings (fatigue) both in Charpy (DIN 53 453) and IFWI (Figure 1). Charpy specimens were fractured at $v=3.7$ m/s with a hammer of 3.63 kg (25J), whereas the plates in IFWI were subjected to impact at $v=10$ m/s (5.17 kg; 258J). Impact fatigue of the beams and plates were carried out at comparable testing conditions, as far as the impact speed ($v \approx 1$ m/s) concerns. Testing conditions were varied by the impact energy, set by the mass of the impactor. The fractograms (e.g. load-displacement traces) were recorded by an AFS-MK4 fractoscope of Ceast (Torino, Italy).

The damage zone development during impact fatigue by the IFWI method was followed by ultrasonic C-scanning, whereas this was extended by light microscopic (LM) and X-ray radiographic (Feinfocus, Berenbostel, FRG) measurements for the Charpy beams. C-scanning of the specimens from both sides occurred by an ultrasonic device (Panametrics, Ithaca, USA) in reflection mode using 5 MHz focused transducers.

Figure 1. Impact testing configurations and size of the specimens used

3. RESULTS

3.1. Impact Fracture Behavior

Figure 2 portrays that interleaving improves the fracture resistance of the composites both at Charpy (Figure 2a) and IFWI conditions (Figure 2b). This improvement is very moderate in the latter case. On the other hand, no effect of the number and position of the interleaving layers could be resolved.

Figure 2. Effects of the position and numbers of the interleaves on the impact fracture of crossed-ply laminates in Charpy (a) and IFWI tests (b), respectively
Note: E_{total} denotes the energy required to break the specimens

3.2. Impact Fatigue Behavior

3.2.1. Charpy Tests

The number of impacts (NOI) at an energy of 2.82 J required to the "total failure" of the Charpy specimens is depicted in Figure 3. "Total failure" was defined when the crack path along the thickness became continuous. Considering the scatter range of $\pm 10\%$, one could conclude from Figure 3, that interleaving does not improve the resistance to impact fatigue at all. This can be explained by the rather sharp edge of the impacting hammer (having an radius of curvature of 2 mm), which influences the breakdown process considerably. The failure sequence is depicted schematically in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Number of repeated impacts with an energy of 2.82 J causing total failure of the Charpy specimens

Figure 4. Failure mode in Charpy tests based on LM and X-ray radiographic observations, schematically

Lowering the impact energy to 1.39 J still retained the ranking (No. 2, 3 and 4 were the best), however, with a fundamental change in the failure mode. In this case delaminations extended mostly on the compression side (in few specimens alternatively on the tensile side) without transverse matrix cracking. The delamination growth was reflected in the fractograms by a broadening in the load-displacement rebound curves. Impacting was ceased when complete delamination along the length of the Charpy specimens (cf. Figure 1) occurred. Based on the above results one can accept that this Charpy technique is not the most proper one of establishing the resistance to impact fatigue, so that further efforts have been focused on IFWI.

3.2.2. IFWI Tests

Figure 5 summarizes the impact fatigue performance of the laminates at repeated impact loadings with different energies. The impacting dart ended in a hemispherical tip (radius of curvature =10 mm; cf. Figure 1). Although there is a scatter in the ranking of the composite plates by impacting them with different energies, one can state that the resistance to impact fatigue increases with increasing number of the interleaves. "Total failure" was supposed to occur when the damage zone size according to C-scans from the bottom of the impacted plates reached that of the supporting ring of the IFWI test (compare Figures 1 and 6).

Figure 5. Number of repeated impacts required to the "total failure" of the plates at different energies in IFWI-tests

The failure mode in IFWI differs basically from that of Charpy. This is mostly due to differences in the loading mode (biaxial and uniaxial, respectively). Figure 6 clearly indicates that damage disseminates along a cone across the thickness of the plates. This agrees with the failure models proposed by several authors (e.g. [5] with references therein).

Figure 6. Development of the damage zone in function of the impact loadings both at the top and bottom of the plates on the example of the composite No. 5 (cf. Table 1)

This observation suggests that the presence of A layers on the tensile side may eventually be beneficial at biaxial loading.

The extension of the damage zone will be checked after sectioning the plates by LM and X-ray techniques. In addition, works are in progress in order to determine the residual properties in compression.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It was established that the effect of interleaving layers (both their position and number) on the impact fatigue performance of crossed-ply composites strongly depends on the testing configuration, involving the loading mode (uni- or biaxial), impact energy and shape of the impactor (radius of curvature). Further investigations are needed therefore to determine the right positioning of the interleaving layer(s).

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